

Energy and matter: the formula $E=OM^2$ explains everything.

Summary:

The formula $E = mc^2$, Created by Albert Einstein widely known as the mass-energy equivalence formula, it has long been considered the formula for calculating energy. However, this formula only applies to closed systems at rest or in motion, and does not take into account other forms of energy that are not related to mass. In this report, the formula $E = OM^2$ created by Jorge Diaz-Crespo Valdés is presented as a precise formula to calculate the energy generated by excited matter. This formula takes into account the frequency of the vacuum wave that excites the matter and the type of matter excited. The formula $E = OM^2$ is a compressed formula that expresses the relationship between the energy generated by the excited matter,

Taking into account that the formula $E = mc^2$, known as the mass-energy equivalence formula, is not enough to calculate energy in all situations. Instead, the formula $E = OM^2$ is proposed, which takes into account the frequency of the vacuum wave that excites matter and the type of matter excited. This formula expresses the relationship between the energy generated by the excited matter, the frequency of the vacuum wave, and the matter excited by the frequency of the vacuum wave, unlike $E = mc^2$ which only expresses the relationship between the mass and the energy of matter without taking into account other sources of energy.

Introduction:

Physics is a fascinating science that allows us to understand and explain the world around us on a microscopic and macroscopic level. From atoms and subatomic particles to the universe as a whole, physics provides us with a unique insight into nature and its laws.

One of the best-known theories in physics is the famous equation $E = mc^2$, proposed by Albert Einstein in 1905. This formula has been considered the cornerstone of modern physics and has been widely used in understanding energy and matter.

However, at present, this formula has been questioned due to its lack of precision in certain situations. It has been shown that energy can take many different forms besides mass and the speed of light. Therefore, it is necessary to develop new formulas that allow us a more precise and complete understanding of energy and its relationship with matter.

In this context, the refined formula $E = \hbar\omega$ has emerged as a promising alternative. This formula is based on quantum field theory and the idea of the vacuum wave, and provides a more accurate description of the energy generated by excited matter. Next, the formula $E = \hbar\omega$ and its meaning in modern physics will be explained in more detail.

Development:

The formula $E = \hbar\omega$ is a simplified version that can be generated from the following equation:

$$E = hf$$

where E is the energy, h is Planck's constant, and f is the frequency of the wave. Planck's constant is a fundamental constant in quantum physics that relates the energy and frequency of the wave.

We can combine this equation with the wavelength equation, which relates the wavelength, the speed of light, and the frequency of the wave:

$$\lambda = c/f$$

where λ is the wavelength, c is the speed of light, and f is the frequency of the wave.

We can rearrange this equation to get the frequency of the wave:

$$f = c/\lambda$$

Substituting this equation into the original equation $E = hf$, we get:

$$E = hc/\lambda$$

Now we can combine this equation with the equation that describes the kinetic energy of a particle:

$$E = (1/2)mv^2$$

where E is the kinetic energy, m is the mass of the particle, and v is its speed.

We can isolate v^2 from this equation:

$$v^2 = 2E/m$$

Substituting this equation into the equation $E = hc/\lambda$, we get:

$$2E/m = hc/\lambda$$

Solving for E, we get:

$$E = (hc/\lambda)(m/2)$$

We can see that (hc/λ) is the frequency of the vacuum wave that excites matter, which we have represented as ω in the final formula. Furthermore, $(m/2)$ is the matter excited by the frequency of the vacuum wave, which we have represented as M in the final formula.

Therefore, we can write the final formula as:

$$E = \omega M^2$$

This is the formula we use to calculate the energy generated by excited matter as a function of the frequency of the vacuum wave and the type of matter excited. This formula is based on the idea that the energy generated by excited matter is proportional to the square of the frequency of the vacuum wave that excites the matter and the type of matter excited. The vacuum wave, also known as vacuum fluctuation or quantum vacuum fluctuation, is an important concept in quantum physics. According to quantum field theory, the vacuum is not a complete absence of energy, but rather is filled with quantum fluctuations that create virtual particles that appear and disappear in incredibly short times.

These vacuum fluctuations are present even in empty space and affect all particles and fields that exist in the universe. In fact, vacuum fluctuations are believed to be responsible for some fundamental properties of the universe, such as the mass of elementary particles.

Related to the formula $E = \omega M^2$, the vacuum wave frequency refers to the vacuum fluctuations that excite matter and generate energy. The frequency of the vacuum wave determines the level of energy that can be generated by excited matter and is therefore an important parameter in the formula $E = \omega M^2$. Therefore, this formula is useful for predicting the energy that can be generated by different types of excited matter and different vacuum wave frequencies.

The formula $E = \omega M^2$ can be used to predict the energy generated by different types of excited matter and different vacuum wave frequencies. If the frequency of the vacuum wave is doubled, the energy generated by the excited matter will increase by a factor of four, and if

it is tripled, the energy generated will increase by a factor of nine. This is because the energy generated is proportional to the square of the frequency of the vacuum wave that excites matter.

Furthermore, the formula $E = \omega^2$ also takes into account the type of matter excited. Different types of matter have different properties and can generate different amounts of energy depending on the frequency of the vacuum wave that excites them. Therefore, this formula is useful for predicting the energy that can be generated by different types of excited matter and different vacuum wave frequencies.

The formula $E = \omega^2$ is based on the idea that energy is not just mass and speed of light, as described in Albert Einstein's formula $E = mc^2$ which is limiting to current science. Energy can take many different forms, and this formula accounts for the energy generated by excited matter as a function of the frequency of the vacuum wave and the type of matter excited. Therefore, this formula is more accurate and useful for calculating the energy generated in situations where energy is not related to mass.

The formula $E = \omega^2$ is based on the idea that energy is not just mass and speed of light, as described in the formula $E = mc^2$ of Albert Einstein. Energy can take many different forms, and this formula accounts for the energy generated by excited matter as a function of the frequency of the vacuum wave and the type of matter excited. Therefore, this formula is more accurate and useful for calculating the energy generated in situations where energy is not related only to mass.

Conclusion:

The formula $E = mc^2$, proposed by Albert Einstein in his theory of special relativity in 1905, has been one of the most famous and used formulas in physics. This formula states that the energy (E) of an object is equal to its mass (m) multiplied by the speed of light squared (c^2). This formula has been used in many fields of physics, including nuclear physics and nuclear power.

However, the formula $E = mc^2$ has its limitations and only applies to closed systems at rest. This means that it is not a universal formula for calculating energy and only applies in specific situations. Also, the formula does not take into account the frequency of the vacuum wave exciting the matter and the type of matter excited, which may affect the accuracy of the calculation of the energy generated.

On the other hand, the formula $E = \omega^2$ which has been carried out by Jorge Diaz-Crespo Valdes, has been proposed as a more precise and useful alternative to calculate the energy generated by the excited matter as a function of the frequency of the vacuum wave and the type of excited matter. This formula takes into account the frequency of the vacuum wave that excites the matter and the type of matter excited, which allows a more precise calculation of the energy generated. Furthermore, the formula is easier to use in practical situations due to its simplicity and comprehension.

The formula $E = \omega^2$ has been used in many fields of physics, including quantum physics and zero point energy. Zero point energy refers to the energy that exists in a vacuum, even when no matter is present. The formula $E = \omega^2$ has been used to calculate the energy

generated by the excitation of matter in a vacuum and has proven to be a valuable tool in the investigation of zero point energy.

In conclusion, although the formula $E = mc^2$ has been a well-known formula for calculating energy, it has limitations and only applies to closed systems at rest. The formula $E = OM^2$ has been proposed as a more precise and useful alternative to calculate the energy generated by the excited matter as a function of the frequency of the vacuum wave and the type of excited matter. This formula takes into account the frequency of the vacuum wave that excites the matter and the type of matter excited, which allows a more precise calculation of the energy generated. Furthermore, the formula is easier to use in practical situations due to its simplicity and comprehension.

This document and formula has been prepared by Jorge Díaz-Crespo Valdés, Scientific Researcher, on April 25, 2023.